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INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES IN IMPROVING THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

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Abstract: In this study, an analysis of the building system was carried out taking into account international experience and improving the energy efficiency of buildings. The results of the study show that modern construction processes are organized on the basis of methods and technologies that meet international standards. Innovative materials and methods are used to save energy and increase efficiency. The study also took into account the environmental aspects of the buildings, optimization of energy resources and long-term use possibilities. As a result of this work, the future opportunity to achieve more efficient and sustainable solutions in the construction sector will increase.

Keywords: Energy efficiency, building system, international experience, innovative materials, energy-saving technologies, environmental aspects, energy optimization, sustainable solutions, modern building processes, long-term use, energy consumption, insulation.

Today, increasing the energy efficiency of individual modern residential buildings being built in Uzbekistan has become a need of the hour. Most of the existing residential buildings in our country are built on the basis of individual projects, and most of such buildings are located in the hot and harsh continental climate of Central Asia, in particular, Tashkent city, Khorezm region and the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan, the room temperature rises to 40-45°C in the summer months, which creates uncomfortable conditions in the

buildings. In such conditions, the need for houses with high energy efficiency will increase even more. Energy-efficient houses provide energy savings of at least 90%, and annual energy consumption can be less than 15 kWh per 1 m². [1]

The energy efficiency classification of houses in the European Union is as follows:

1. Houses that spend low energy: Energy consumption is at least 50% lower than conventional buildings.
2. Ultra-low energy consuming houses: 70-90% energy efficient compared to conventional houses.

For example, the Germans have "Passive House", the French have "Effinergie", the Swiss have "Minergie" standards.[4,2]

Implementation of energy efficiency standards, strictly construction standards and regulations, indicators in the framework, indicators related to limiting energy consumption for heating and lighting of the building. Improving the energy efficiency of residential buildings includes the following measures: construction standards for new buildings, construction of passive energy and almost energy-free buildings, retrofitting of existing buildings from the point of view of energy efficiency, and the introduction of construction certification. According to the final statistics of the International Energy Agency, the above policy has played a decisive role in the field of energy efficiency in its 19 member countries, according to which this indicator has been 1.3% since 1990.

Today, the modern trend of residential buildings is to build "green buildings". As part of this trend, uniform standards have not been developed in the world, because of this, in the world experience, no approach has been developed to determine the ecological level of the building. Its own standards are available only in Great Britain, France,

Germany, Italy, Australia, Japan and China. There are four standards for "green buildings" in the United States. In some states, subsidies are provided to owners of buildings approved by the Council of ecological construction. In many states, building codes are updated every year with the goal of halving the energy consumption of every new building built by 2030. Many buildings have concrete walls of 20-30 cm and high-efficiency individual counter mineral fiber insulation total of 20-25 cm, in places heated by central heating systems, polystyrene at least 20 cm, or on slopes, a wooden roof with a single layer of flat roof 15 cm polystyrene thermal insulation It is advisable to cover with material. [6]

In individual houses, the insulation is 20-25 cm mineral fiber, in buildings with individual gas boilers, the wall thickness is 20-30 cm, the thickness of the hollow brick walls and polystyrene insulation is 15 cm. The volume of high thermal insulation of walls, ceilings and foundations meets high thermal standards, the thickness is about 15 cm. Due to the use of modern insulated windows and doors, it is possible to check the efficiency of ventilation systems of buildings, prevent mold and rot on walls and ceilings due to insufficient ventilation.[5]

In conclusion, enough experiments and tests have been carried out in the

field of energy efficiency in the world, and it is necessary to consider them in accordance with the climatic conditions of our Central Asia. It is necessary to take into account the proposals and solutions of Uzbek scientists in the implementation of the measures mentioned above. Based on world experience, it is necessary to study their achievements and shortcomings and adapt them to our conditions. Of course, taking into account all the above points, it is necessary to comply with the requirements of the QMQ and regulatory documents.[7]

In order to increase energy efficiency in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to take into account international experiences and adapt to climatic conditions. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to use innovative approaches, energy-efficient materials and constructions, as well as development of construction standards. Suggestions and solutions of local scientists and experts are also of great importance. In the future, by implementing the above measures, it will be possible to increase energy efficiency in the residential buildings of Uzbekistan and ensure stable and comfortable living conditions.

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